

Diversity of frugivorous and omnivorous birds in different stages of ecological succession in Amazon Rainforest fragments

Fabio Rossano Dario

Instituto de Pesquisas e Estudos da Vida Silvestre,
Rua Leonardo Mota, 66/184, Butantã, CEP 05586-090, São Paulo – SP, Brasil

E-mail address: fabiorossano@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

The diversity of birds is directly correlated with the structure of the forest. Any interfering with the vegetation produces direct effects on the avifauna through the increase, decrease, or alternation of two key attributes: food and shelter. Thus, the composition of life in the forest is altered as changes occur in vegetation that directly interferes with the population structure of the avifauna, be those changes natural or anthropic. This study was realized in fragments of the Amazon Rainforest, and the main objective was to analyze the behavior of frugivorous and omnivorous birds in three different stages of ecological succession. In forest environments where a vertical stratification of resources occurs, these species are distributed occupying a in a high diversity of trophic niches. The diversity and density of the frugivorous and omnivorous birds in the forest fragments in medium and advanced stage of ecological succession could be directly correlated not only with the structure of the forest, but also to the fact that these birds feed almost exclusively on abundant and easy to find food sources - shrub and tree fruit of certain vegetable species that are naturally abundant in the rainforest understory layer.

Keywords: birds, frugivory, ecological succession, Amazon Rainforest

1. INTRODUCTION

The Amazon Rainforest is one of the principal Brazilian biome and is formed by dense tropical forests and associated ecosystems, and represents over half of the planet's remaining

rainforests, and comprises the largest and most biodiverse tract of tropical rainforest in the world.

The diversity of fauna is more directly correlated with the structure of the forest than the quantity of plant species in the natural environment [1]. Tropical forests possess a large variation of internal microclimates, taking advantage of both its horizontal and vertical structure. The increase in structural complexity of the vegetation on various vertical levels makes new forms of occupancy of the environment possible. The increase in the number of animal species is principally due to the increase of both the new food guilds and the number of species in the existing guilds [2].

The composition of the fauna is the product of an evolutionary process. Each animal species is dependent on certain characteristics of the vegetation and the biological interactions that determine where it will be able to exist [3]. The structure of the forest, the distance between trees, the different types of vegetation, as well as the special arrangement of the forest elements that constitute the landscape determine the patterns of movement of these animals and explain a large part of the spatial variation in the number and categories of tree visits. Among the many factors thought to contribute to the high bird species richness in the Neotropics is the high diversity of habitat and microhabitat types, some of which are unique to tropical regions [4, 5]. The increase in structural complexity of the vegetation on various vertical levels makes new forms of occupancy of the environment possible [6]. The increase in the number of bird species is principally due to the increase of both the new food guilds and the number of species in the existing guilds [2].

The guild of the birds frugivorous is principally represented in the Amazon Forest, by species of the Cracidae, Psittacidae, Cotingidae, Trogonidae, and Pipridae. These species could be considered the principle seed dispersing agents in the Amazon Forest [7].

Omnivorous birds were an important guild in the Amazon Rainforest. The guild of the omnivores is composed of species which eat grains, fruit, seeds, and small arthropods, contributing considerably to the dispersion of seeds. Omnivores on the edges of the forest are the main representatives of this group, in Amazon Rainforest, especially for species of the following families: Tyrannidae, Icteridae, Ramphastidae, Vireonidae, Thraupidae, and Fringillidae [8]. The birds are considered the most important bioindicator of the ecosystems quality because they are sensible to the alterations of the environment. The main objective of this study was to analyze if the groups of birds of the both guilds frugivorous and omnivorous were affected by the forest fragmentation, analyzing the diversity of frugivorous and omnivorous birds in different stages of ecological succession in Amazon Rainforest fragments: initial, medium and advance stages.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in Amazon Rainforest areas, situated in Southwest State of the Maranhão, Brazil, located at latitude 05°03'S to 05°15'S and longitude 47°33'W to 47°41'W, along the seasons of 1997. The climate of the region is the Aw type according to Köppen's classification. The annual average rainfall is over 1,300 mm, concentrated in the summer. The annual medium temperature ranges is 26 °C.

Three different natural environments were studied: a) Forest fragments in initial stage of ecological succession; b) Forest fragments in medium stage of ecological succession; c)

Forest fragments in advanced stage of ecological succession. The vegetal community of these fragments is part of a forest subjected to human interference.

The forest fragments in initial stage of ecological succession have only one stratum with trees varying in average height between two and six meters. The total area covered with early growth was circa 12,000 hectares. The estimated basal area was $2.81 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{ha}^{-1}$ and densities ranging from 1,200 to 1,400 trees·ha⁻¹. A low species diversity was observed, $H = 2.80 \text{ nats ind}^{-1}$. In the forest fragments in medium stage of secondary regeneration are recognizable three vertical strata of the vegetation: herbaceous stratum, understory and canopy stratum. The canopy stratum is composed of the crowns of large sized trees, with sparse trees varying in average height between 8 and 18 meters. The total area covered in this stage of ecological succession was circa 8,000 hectares. The estimated basal area was $2.78 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{ha}^{-1}$ and densities ranging from 900 to 1,100 trees·ha⁻¹. A high species diversity was observed, $H = 3.68 \text{ nats ind}^{-1}$.

In the forest fragments in advanced stage of secondary regeneration are recognizable three vertical strata of the vegetation: herbaceous stratum, understory and canopy stratum. The canopy stratum is composed of the crowns of large sized trees, with sparse trees varying in average height between 10 and 30 meters. The total area covered in this stage of ecological succession was circa 12,000 hectares. The estimated basal area was $39.83 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{ha}^{-1}$ and densities ranging from 600 to 800 trees·ha⁻¹. A high species diversity was observed, $H = 4.24 \text{ nats ind}^{-1}$.

The understory is characterized by the dominance of shrubs between 0.80 and 5 meters tall and the outstanding species in this stratum are of the families Melastomataceae, Rubiaceae, Fabaceae, Euphorbiaceae and Myrtaceae being these the most important families to the fruits production to the fauna. The herbaceous stratum (generally until 0.80 meters tall) is predominated by ferns, terrestrial bromeliads and herbs as heliconias.

The method used to sample the avifauna specimens was the technique of observations per point-counts developed by Blondel *et al.* [9]. The location of the points used for this census was randomly chosen and was representative of the whole areas: for each sample, the point was sorted independently among previously determined points covering the whole areas. The points were marked at least 200 meters apart to avoid over-representation of species with long-range voices.

The observations were realized in the first hours after the dawn and during the twilight. The samplings were accomplished in 38 days in two seasons: summer and winter of 1997 (in a total of 240 hours distributed in 720 samples). The duration of each point census is 20 minutes. The birds' identification was visual and mainly through the bird vocalization. The birds that overflying the areas without to perch on tree was not analyzed, because their dependence to the places were unlikely.

To the scientific nomenclature and taxonomic order was used the new systematic list of CBRO [10]. To determine if the samples were enough, were plotted the accumulated number of species against the total number of hours of observation. Since the curve reached a plateau, it was possible to conclude that the samples were enough for the registration of most species existent in each site.

The classification of the species in agreement with the respective ecological groups was based on that proposed for Amazon Rainforest bird communities by Willis [11]. This study was limited to trace the similar relationships of feeding habitats and preferred foraging strata in the vegetation for frugivorous and omnivorous bird's species.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Taking into account 240 hours of observations, it was possible to register a total of 105 frugivorous and omnivorous birds' species. Of these, a total of 47 birds' species was recorded in the forest fragments in the initial stage of ecological succession, and this site was characterized by low diversity. In this anthropic environment, birds' species who occupied the edge of the forest fragments were the most representative. Understory birds species have little importance, because the understory is inexpressive.

In the forest fragments in medium stage of ecological succession were registered 71 frugivorous and omnivorous birds' species. According to results, birds' species who occupied the edge of the forest fragments had the same representativeness that in the forest fragments in the initial stage of ecological succession, but understory frugivores had a good representativeness.

In the forest fragments in the advanced stage of ecological succession were registered a total of 85 frugivorous and omnivorous birds' species. This fact was already expected, since it is common in mature forests with great vertical heterogeneity [12, 13]. The increase in the number of frugivorous and omnivorous birds' species, from forest fragments in initial stages to the forest fragments in more advanced stages (from 47 to 85 birds species) is the result of the better vegetation structure in the more advanced stages. Studies realized by Bierregaard & Lovejoy [14] in similars forests in Amazon Rainforest also showed birds' communities much diversified. This fact is because the forest fragments in more advanced stages are the most important centers of colonization of forest species [7, 15].

The significant presence of the understory frugivorous birds in forest fragments in the medium and advanced stages of ecological succession is in reason of the vertical structure of these with three strata of the vegetation: herbaceous stratum, understorey and canopy stratum [16].

Of the plant species of the Amazon Rainforest, the majority of plant species very important as fruit producers, and are eaten by diversity of fauna species. The genus *Palicourea* (Rubiaceae family) comprehends dozens of shrub and small tree species distributed in the understory layer of the tropical rainforest. Their fruit are small berries and are fairly attractive due to their dark coloration. Among the frugivorous birds that feed on these species were members of the Pipridae family [17, 18]. Others genera of the Rubiaceae family in the understory layer of the tropical rainforest have species that produce fruit for fauna, such as *Alibertia*, *Bothriospora*, *Psychotria* and *Randia* [19].

Some species of the *Trichilia* genus (Meliaceae family), typical of understory layer of the tropical rainforest possess attributes evident to birds, such as coloration and accessibility of the fruit positioned closer to the extremities with long pedicels. The physical accessibility, determined by the structure of the fruit and their position on the branch, can determine in large part the birds' choice [20]. This could explain the large quantity of bird species that eat the fruit of these plants.

Species of the *Miconia* genus (Melastomataceae family), also typical of understory layer of the tropical rainforest and highly of great abundance in the present study in the forest fragments in the advanced stage of ecological succession, have small, rounded fruit consumed by birds [21]. Many small seeds are embedded in its sweet pulp, another characteristic of plants that belong to secondary formations that invest more in the number of seeds than nutritional reserves for the establishment of its descendants [22].

Snow [22] studied 19 shrub and tree species of the *Miconia* genus in the Amazon Rainforest. Each species produced fruit during a specific season of the year, and none bore fruit all year long. Nevertheless, fruiting season of all of the 19 species did cover the whole year. The author suggested that the various *Miconia* species compete among themselves for the services of animal seed dispersers like manakins (*Pipridae* family) and, to reduce the competition between them for dispersers, they segment the market for dispersers, offering fruit in different seasons of the year. In the present study, the manakins were registered only in medium and advanced stage of ecological succession in the forest fragments. A great diversity of bird species eats fruit from Melastomataceae species besides manakins, and in general these plants are recognized as one of the most important food sources of small frugivorous birds. In tropical forests, where manakins are one of the most numerous birds, they seem to be the most important dispersers of Melastomataceae species. However, the tanagers (*Thraupidae* family) are also important dispersers and, in medium high forests, substitute manakins as the most important dispersers of Melastomataceae species [23].

Table 1. Number of bird species in different guilds and in different natural environments.

Guilds	Number of species	Environments/Number of species		
		Initial stage	Medium stage	Advanced stage
Canopy frugivores	20	7	14	16
Canopy omnivores	5	1	5	5
Edge omnivores	46	32	32	32
Understory frugivores	34	7	20	32
Total	105	47	71	85

Table 2. List of the bird species in different natural environments grouped into trophic guilds.

GUILDS/Family/ Taxon names	English name	Environments		
		Initial stage	Medium stage	Advanced stage
CANOPY FRUGIVORES				
Cracidae				
<i>Penelope superciliaris</i>	Rusty-margined Guan		X	X
<i>Penelope pileata</i>	White-crested Guan			X

<i>Ortalis motmot</i>	Variable Chachalaca		X	
<i>Ortalis superciliaris</i>	Buff-browed Chachalaca	X	X	X
Psittacidae				
<i>Ara chloropterus</i>	Red-and-green Macaw			X
<i>Guaruba guarouba</i>	Golden Parakeet			X
<i>Psittacara leucophthalmus</i>	White-eyed Parakeet	X		
<i>Aratinga solstitialis</i>	Sun Parakeet	X	X	X
<i>Eupsittula aurea</i>	Peach-fronted Parakeet		X	
<i>Pyrrhura perlata</i>	Crimson-bellied Parakeet			X
<i>Pyrrhura picta</i>	Painted Parakeet			X
<i>Forpus xanthopterygius</i>	Blue-winged Parrotlet		X	X
<i>Brotogeris versicolurus</i>	White-winged Parakeet		X	
<i>Brotogeris chiriri</i>	Yellow-chevroned Parakeet	X	X	X
<i>Brotogeris chrysoptera</i>	Golden-winged Parakeet		X	X
<i>Pionus menstruus</i>	Blue-headed Parrot		X	X
<i>Pionus maximiliani</i>	Scaly-headed Parrot		X	X
<i>Amazona farinosa</i>	Mealy Parrot	X	X	X
<i>Amazona amazonica</i>	Orange-winged Parrot	X	X	X
Icteridae				
<i>Psarocolius decumanus</i>	Crested Oropendola	X	X	X
CANOPY OMNIVORES				
Ramphastidae				
<i>Ramphastos tucanus</i>	White-throated Toucan		X	X
<i>Ramphastos vitellinus</i>	Channel-billed Toucan		X	X
<i>Pteroglossus inscriptus</i>	Lettered Aracari		X	X
<i>Pteroglossus bitorquatus</i>	Red-necked Aracari		X	X
<i>Pteroglossus aracari</i>	Black-necked Aracari	X	X	X

EDGE OMNIVORES				
Tinamidae				
<i>Crypturellus parvirostris</i>	Small-billed Tinamou	X	X	X
<i>Rhynchotus rufescens</i>	Red-winged Tinamou			X
Odontophoridae				
<i>Odontophorus gujanensis</i>	Marbled Wood-Quail			X
Columbidae				
<i>Patagioenas picazuro</i>	Picazuro Pigeon		X	X
Tityridae				
<i>Pachyramphus viridis</i>	Green-backed Becard			X
<i>Pachyramphus rufus</i>	Cinereous Becard	X		
<i>Pachyramphus polychopterus</i>	White-winged Becard	X	X	X
Rhynchocyclidae				
<i>Tolmomyias sulphurescens</i>	Yellow-olive Flycatcher		X	X
<i>Tolmomyias flaviventris</i>	Yellow-breasted Flycatcher	X	X	X
Tyrannidae				
<i>Camptostoma obsoletum</i>	Southern Beardless-Tyrannulet	X	X	X
<i>Elaenia flavogaster</i>	Yellow-bellied Elaenia	X	X	X
Vireonidae				
<i>Cyclarhis gujanensis</i>	Rufous-browed Peppershrike	X	X	X
<i>Vireo olivaceus</i>	Red-eyed Vireo	X	X	X
<i>Hylophilus thoracicus</i>	Lemon-chested Greenlet	X	X	X
Turdidae				
<i>Turdus nudigenis</i>	Spectacled Thrush	X	X	X
<i>Turdus amaurochalinus</i>	Creamy-bellied Thrush	X	X	X
Mimidae				
<i>Mimus saturninus</i>	Chalk-browed Mockingbird	X		

Passerellidae				
<i>Zonotrichia capensis</i>	Rufous-collared Sparrow	X	X	
Icteridae				
<i>Cacicus cela</i>	Yellow-rumped Cacique	X	X	X
<i>Icterus cayanensis</i>	Epaulet Oriole		X	X
<i>Icterus jamaicaii</i>	Campo Troupial	X	X	X
<i>Gnorimopsar chopi</i>	Chopi Blackbird	X	X	
<i>Chrysomus ruficapillus</i>	Chestnut-capped Blackbird	X		
<i>Molothrus oryzivorus</i>	Giant Cowbird	X		
<i>Molothrus bonariensis</i>	Shiny Cowbird	X		
Thraupidae				
<i>Cissopis leverianus</i>	Magpie Tanager	X	X	X
<i>Schistochlamys melanopis</i>	Black-faced Tanager	X	X	
<i>Schistochlamys ruficapillus</i>	Cinnamon Tanager		X	
<i>Tangara episcopus</i>	Blue-gray Tanager	X	X	X
<i>Tangara sayaca</i>	Sayaca Tanager		X	
<i>Tangara palmarum</i>	Palm Tanager	X	X	X
<i>Tangara cayana</i>	Burnished-buff Tanager	X		X
<i>Nemosia pileata</i>	Hooded Tanager	X		
<i>Conirostrum speciosum</i>	Chestnut-vented Conebill	X		
<i>Lanio luctuosus</i>	White-shouldered Tanager		X	
<i>Tachyphonus rufus</i>	White-lined Tanager	X	X	X
<i>Ramphocelus carbo</i>	Silver-beaked Tanager	X	X	X
<i>Saltatricula atricollis</i>	Black-throated Saltator	X		
<i>Saltator maximus</i>	Buff-throated Saltator	X	X	X
<i>Saltator coerulescens</i>	Grayish Saltator	X	X	X
<i>Saltator similis</i>	Green-winged Saltator		X	X

<i>Saltator grossus</i>	Slate-colored Grosbeak		X	X
Cardinalidae				
<i>Caryothraustes canadensis</i>	Yellow-green Grosbeak		X	X
Fringillidae				
<i>Euphonia chlorotica</i>	Purple-throated Euphonia	X	X	X
<i>Euphonia violacea</i>	Violaceous Euphonia			X
<i>Euphonia cayennensis</i>	Golden-sided Euphonia			X
UNDERSTORY FRUGIVORES				
Tinamidae				
<i>Crypturellus soui</i>	Little Tinamou	X	X	X
<i>Crypturellus undulatus</i>	Undulated Tinamou		X	
<i>Crypturellus tataupa</i>	Tataupa Tinamou		X	
Columbidae				
<i>Patagioenas speciosa</i>	Scaled Pigeon		X	X
<i>Patagioenas cayennensis</i>	Pale-vented Pigeon			X
<i>Patagioenas plumbea</i>	Plumbeous Pigeon	X	X	X
<i>Patagioenas subvinacea</i>	Ruddy Pigeon	X	X	X
<i>Leptotila verreauxi</i>	White-tipped Dove	X	X	X
<i>Leptotila rufaxilla</i>	Gray-fronted Dove	X	X	X
<i>Geotrygon montana</i>	Ruddy Quail-Dove			X
Trogonidae				
<i>Trogon viridis</i>	Green-backed Trogon		X	X
<i>Trogon violaceus</i>	Guianan Trogon			X
Pipridae				
<i>Tyranneutes stolzmanni</i>	Dwarf Tyrant-Manakin			X
<i>Pipra fasciicauda</i>	Band-tailed Manakin			X
<i>Ceratopipra rubrocapilla</i>	Red-headed Manakin		X	X

<i>Manacus manacus</i>	White-bearded Manakin		X	X
<i>Chiroxiphia pareola</i>	Blue-backed Manakin		X	X
Tityridae				
<i>Schiffornis turdina</i>	Thrush-like Schiffornis			X
<i>Tityra inquisitor</i>	Black-crowned Tityra			X
<i>Tityra cayana</i>	Black-tailed Tityra			X
<i>Tityra semifasciata</i>	Masked Tityra		X	X
Cotingidae				
<i>Querula purpurata</i>	Purple-throated Fruitcrow	X	X	X
<i>Lipaugus vociferans</i>	Screaming Piha		X	X
Pipritidae				
<i>Piprites chloris</i>	Wing-barred Piprites			X
Rhynchocyclidae				
<i>Mionectes oleagineus</i>	Ochre-bellied Flycatcher		X	X
Tyrannidae				
<i>Lathrotriccus euleri</i>	Euler's Flycatcher		X	X
<i>Attila spadiceus</i>	Bright-rumped Attila		X	X
Turdidae				
<i>Turdus leucomelas</i>	Pale-breasted Thrush	X	X	X
<i>Turdus fumigatus</i>	Cocoa Thrush			X
Thraupidae				
<i>Hemithraupis guira</i>	Guira Tanager		X	X
<i>Lanio cristatus</i>	Flame-crested Tanager			X
Cardinalidae				
<i>Habia rubra</i>	Scarlet-throated Ant-Tanager			X
<i>Granatellus pelzelni</i>	Rose-breasted Chat			X
<i>Cyanoloxia rothschildii</i>	Rothschild's Blue Grosbeak			X

4. CONCLUSIONS

The integrity and complexity of a forest are the factors that influence the composition, abundance and probably the functions of the assembly of different bird's species. In that way, in forest environments where a vertical stratification of resources occurs, these species are distributed occupying a high diversity of trophic niches. They occupy different heights of the forest and a great diversity of bird species distributed among different trophic guilds, which means ecosystems relatively balanced and of great biological value. The diversity and density of the frugivorous and omnivorous birds in medium and advanced stage of ecological succession in the forest fragments could be directly correlated not only with the structure of the forest but also to the fact that these birds feed almost exclusively on abundant and easy to find food source: shrub and tree fruit of certain vegetable species abundant in rainforest understory layer.

References

- [1] J.P. Lebreton. Incidences avifaunistiques des aménagements forestiers: substitutions *Quercus / Pinus* en milieu subméditerranéen. *Bulletin d'Ecologie* 22 (1991) 213-220.
- [2] M.F. Willson. Avian community organization and habitat structure. *Ecology Monographs* 55 (1974) 1017-1029.
- [3] L.B. MacArthur, R.C. Whitmore. Passerine community composition and diversity in man-altered environments. *West Virginia Forest Notes* 7 (1979) 1-12.
- [4] J. Karr. Seasonality, resource availability, and community diversity in tropical bird communities. *American Naturalist* 110 (1976) 973-994.
- [5] J. Terborgh. Causes of tropical species diversity. *Conar* 1978 (1980) 955-961.
- [6] J. Terborgh, S.K. Robinson, T.P. Parker III, C. Munn, N. Pierpont. Structure and organization of an Amazonian forest bird community. *Ecological Monographs* 60 (1990) 213-238.
- [7] F.R. Dario. Interactions between vegetation and avifauna in Amazon forest. *Asian Journal of Biological and Life Sciences* 3(3) (2013) 190-195.
- [8] F.R. Dario, A. Almeida, F.H. Muniz. Diversity and trophic structure of bird's community in Amazon Rainforest fragments in different stages of ecological succession. *Asian Journal of Biological and Life Sciences* 6(1) (2017) 381-393.
- [9] J. Blondel, C. Ferry, B. Frochot. La méthode des indices ponctuels d'abondance (I.P.A.) ou des relevés d'avifaune par "stations d'écoute". *Alauda* 38 (1970) 55-71.
- [10] Brazilian Ornithological Records Committee. Checklist of the birds of Brazil. *Revista Brasileira de Ornitologia* 23(2) (2015) 91-298.
- [11] E.O. Willis. The compositions of avian communities in remanescents woodlots in southern Brazil. *Papéis Avulsos de Zoologia* 33 (1979) 1-25.

- [12] R.H. MacArthur, J.W. MacArthur. On bird species diversity. *Ecology* 42 (1961) 594-598.
- [13] R.H. MacArthur, J.W. MacArthur, J. Preer. On bird species diversity. II. Prediction of bird census from habitat measurements. *The American Naturalist* 96 (1962) 167-174.
- [14] R.O. Bierregaard Jr., T.E. Lovejoy. Effects of forest fragmentation on Amazonian understory bird communities. *Acta Amazonica* 19 (1989) 215-241.
- [15] R.O. Bierregaard Jr., T.E. Lovejoy, V. Kapos, V.A.A. Santos, R. Hutchings. The biological dynamics of tropical rainforest fragments. *BioScience* 42 (1992) 859-866.
- [16] J. Barlow, C.A. Peres, L.M.P. Henriques, P.C. Stouffer, J.M. Wunderle. The responses of understory birds to forest fragmentation, logging and wildfires: An Amazonian synthesis. *Biological Conservation* 128 (2006) 182-192.
- [17] C.P. Coelho. Frugivoria e possível dispersão em *Palicourea macrobotrys* (Rubiaceae). *Revista Brasileira de Biociências* 5 (2007) 180-182.
- [18] H.F. Howe, G.A.V. Kerckhove. Fecundity and seed dispersal of a tropical tree. *Ecology* 60(1) (1979) 180-189.
- [19] L.A. Maia, L.M. Santos, P. Parolin. Germinação de sementes de *Bothriospora corymbosa* (Rubiaceae) recuperadas do trato digestório de *Tripottheus angulatus* (sardinha) no Lago Camaleão, Amazônia Central. *Acta Amazonica* 37 (2007) 321-326.
- [20] B.A. Loiselle, J.G. Blake. Diets of understory fruit-eating birds in Costa Rica: seasonality and resource abundance. *Studies in Avian Biology* 13 (1990) 91-103.
- [21] P.K. Maruyama, E. Alves-Silva, C. Melo. Oferta qualitativa e quantitativa de frutos em espécies ornitócoricas do gênero *Miconia* (Melastomataceae). *Revista Brasileira de Biociências* 5 (2007) 672-674.
- [22] D.W. Snow. A possible selective factor in the evolution of fruiting seasons in tropical forest. *Oikos* 15 (1965) 274-281.
- [23] F.G. Stiles, L. Rosselli. Consumption of fruits of the Melastomataceae by birds - How diffuse is coevolution? *Vegetatio* 108 (1993) 57-73.

(Received 16 October 2017; accepted 30 October 2017)